

Vibronic coherences in light harvesting nanotubes: unravelling the role of dark states

Sandra Doria, Mariangela Di Donato, Raffaele Borrelli, Maxim F. Gelin, Justin Caram, Marco Pagliai,
Paolo Foggi, and Andrea Lapini

Supplementary Information

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S1 Experimental details

The experimental configuration used for the acquisition of pump-probe spectra and for the two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy (2DES) in the pump-probe geometry is a modified version of the set-up already described in our former paper [20] and it is schematically reported in figure S1. Briefly, a fraction of the energy output (approximately 450 mW, 1KHz, 40 fs) from a regenerative amplifier (Coherent Legend-Elite USP) is directed to a home-built non-collinear optical parametric amplifier (NOPA). NOPA generates chirped pulses (max output $2\mu\text{J}$ energy per pulse) centered roughly around 600-610 nm with an asymmetric shape possessing 60 nm FWHM. The pulses are then compressed by means of a couple of chirped mirrors (DCM10 Venteon): after a total of 11 bounces the dispersion introduced by the optics and cryostat windows are very well compensated at the sample region, in such a way that the duration retrieved by PG-FROG analysis is around 12 fs. The spectrum and FROG trace retrieved by the simulation are reported in figure S2.

Figure S1: *Experimental setup scheme: M, mirror; SM, spherical mirror; PM, phase mask; DLw1, delay stage w1 axis; DCM10, chirped mirror; DL2, delay stage; WD, wedge window. NOPA is highlighted in the purple frame.*

Figure S2: *a) Experimental Polarization gated Frog (PG-Frog) trace; b) Retrieved PG-Frog trace; c) Retrieved pulse duration and d) retrieved Spectrum; e) Experimental spectrum of NOPA output.*

After chirped mirror reflection, the BS1 broadband 50% beam-splitter (layertec) generates pump (reflected portion) and probe (transmitted one) pulses. We then introduce our new experimental scheme, capable of generating two collinear pump pulses (E_1 and E_2) with very good phase difference stability, allowing to get purely absorptive 2D spectra in the pseudo-pump-probe geometry.

After reflection from BS1, the pump portion is focused by the spherical mirror SM4, $f=200$ mm, on the phase grating PM (Edinburgh optics, fused silica, 72 g/mm) and two identical replicas (E_1 and E_2) are generated on the ± 1 order of the grating. The two replicas are then collimated by a spherical mirror (SM3, $f=200$ mm). Mirror M12 is then used to retroreflect the two beams back on the PM phase grating at a slightly different height. The mask in front of M12 assures that only E_1 and E_2 are retroreflected. Once E_1 and E_2 are focused back on PM, a fraction of each beam is refracted on the zeroth order of the grating, generating two collinear pulses. Two couples of fused silica wedge windows (1° deg wedge angle, DLw1 and DLw2) are introduced in the optical path between SM3 and M12 and the mutual lateral shift (mechanical translation stage, Physik-Instrumente) is used to finely adjust and scan the coherence delay t_1 between E_1 and E_2 . This scheme assures an absolute position reproducibility of the wedges of ± 0.1 micron, in such a

way that the error on the reproducibility of the $E_1 - E_2$ delay is ± 8 as.

After PM, E_1 and E_2 are re-collimated by SM4. Finally, they are separated from the incoming beam by M13, at a slightly different height. E_1 and E_2 are then directed towards the DL2 translation stage (Physik-Instrumente) to adjust the population delay T. The two beams are then overlapped with the probe and focused on the sample by SM5. Reference beam generated by BS2, passes through the sample but it is not overlapped with pump and probe beams. Finally probe and reference are collected after the sample by SM6 (located at 2f with respect to the sample position), focused at the entrance of a monochromator system, frequency dispersed and imaged on two separated array detectors (256 pxs, Hamamatsu). 2D spectra have been obtained by Fourier-transforming the time domain signal recorded by modulating the intensity of E_1 by an optical chopper and synchronously scanning the relative delay by adjusting the wedge couple on E_2 (unmodulated beam).

In details: for each delay t_1 between E_1 and E_2 , the beam is chopped at half the rep rate of the laser. The differential signal as a function of t_1 is then calculated in a pump-probe classical scheme where the subscripts on and off refer to E_1 alternatively on and off:

$$S(t_1, \omega_3, T) = \left(\frac{I_{probe}(t_1, \omega_3, T)}{I_{ref}(t_1, \omega_3, T)} \right)_{on} \left(\frac{I_{ref}(t_1, \omega_3, T)}{I_{probe}(t_1, \omega_3, T)} \right)_{off} \quad (S1)$$

Such an acquisition scheme generates two different kind of signal in the direction of the probe beam: the pump probe signal coming from the interaction of the chopped E_1 pulse plus the probe pulse with the sample and the *Rephasing* plus *non-Rephasing* signal coming from the interaction of E_1 , E_2 and probe pulses with the sample. Within our scheme, where we adjust the delay between E_1 and E_2 moving the E_2 pulse, the pump probe signal is due to the chopped E_1 pulse and can be considered as a constant: it does not change as a function of t_1 because the delay between E_1 and probe pulse is a constant. Concerning the signal $S(t_1, \omega_3, T)$, we reported in Fig. S3b an example of raw data acquired on the maximum of the inner-wall bleaching band at various temperature for population time (delay between and probe) of 40 fs. We employed a sampling rate of 0.5 fs point and each time domain signal has been zero padded to a factor of 2. Prior to zero padding a gaussian window function is usually applied to minimized artifacts in 2D spectral shape. However, due to the very long sampled delays the windowing effect can be reasonably neglected and the differences of band shape with or without window function is very small. Once window function and zero padding have been applied, the data are Fourier Transformed. Results are reported in Fig. S3b. The pump-probe contribution, superimposed on the time domain signal as constant value, gives rise to a zero-frequency contribution in the frequency domain and can be separated.

Figure S3: *a) example of raw data acquired on the maximum of the inner-wall bleaching band at various temperature at population time of 40 fs; b) Fourier transformation of the raw data after postprocessing consisting in application of gaussian window function and zero-padding technique.*

Our experimental setup allows us to record 2D spectra in the pump-probe geometry without the usage of a pulse shaper. The two collinear pulses are indeed generated with a double pass in a common thin phase grating. In the pump-probe geometry the E_1 and E_2 fields are collinear and the phase matching conditions imply that the *Rephasing* and *Non-Rephasing* signal are emitted collinearly in respect with the E_3 field, which acts as the probe pulse. In other words the E_3 pulse that stimulate the *Rephasing* signal along the direction $-\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2 + \vec{k}_3$ and the *Non-Rephasing* signal along the $-\vec{k}_1 - \vec{k}_2 + \vec{k}_3$ in the BOXCARS geometry will now stimulate both contributions along its propagation direction. The two contributions are emitted simultaneously and they have intrinsically the same phase. The E_3 pulse acts as the local oscillator, directly heterodyning the sum of *Rephasing* and *Non-Rephasing*, meaning that the Fourier transform of the time domain signal is already the purely absorptive spectrum.

In the following Fig. S4 we report a phase stability test performed on 1 hour running measurement. We acquired and spectrally resolved the interference pattern between E_1 and E_2 modulating the intensity of E_1 .

Figure S4: *$E_1 - E_2$ phase difference stability monitored over 1h of running measurements.*

Pump-Probe spectra have been obtained simply blocking E_2 and adjusting the population delay with respect to the probe pulse by the DL2 delay stage.

The liquid nitrogen cryostat containing the sample is represented in the picture of Fig. S5, together with the built-in apparatus for continuous movement and vibration isolation.

Figure S5: *Sample area of the setup used for broadband TAS and 2DES measurements. The cryostat is mounted on a vertical translator, kept under continuous motion by means of a stepper motor controlled by home-made electronic equipment and software. Critical aspects are the weight of the cryostat and the necessity to minimize the vibration of the sample holder caused by the cryostat motion, in order to minimize noise and scattering, particularly during the 2DES experiments. To minimize mechanical vibrations, the gear connected to the stepper motor is fixed to the frame that surrounds the optical table with by means of a resistant homemade metal structure.*

S2 Temperature dependent steady state spectroscopy

Figure S6: *a*) Representative temperature dependent absorption and emission profiles fit to Voigt functions. *b*) FWHM of IW absorption and emission feature from 5 to 300K. Fit to temperature-dependent Lorentzian linewidth. Reprinted with permission from Nano Letters 2016 16 (11), 6808-6815. Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society.

S3 Broadband pump probe results

S3.1 Full Maps and kinetics at different temperatures

Figure S7: 80K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the *J*-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S8: 100K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S9: 120K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S10: 140K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S11: 160K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S12: 180K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S13: 200K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S14: 220K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S15: 240K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

Figure S16: 260K: top) full time-frequency map collected upon broadband excitation of the J-aggregate in sugar matrix. The right panel shows a zoom of the spectra at short time delay. bottom) single-frequency time traces recorded at the minimum peak (GSB/SE) of inner and outer wall. The right panel shows a zoom of the traces for the initial 5 picoseconds pump-probe delays.

S3.2 Wavelet analysis

Figure S17: Wavelet analysis performed on the kinetic traces taken at the maximum absorption of inner wall at different temperatures.

S3.3 Global analysis

We performed Global analysis with “Glortaran” software [34] to further analyse the excited state dynamics, applying a sequential unidirectional decay scheme with three kinetic components. Although we believe that the strong oscillations occurring at low temperature prevents to extract properly reliable time-constants from the global fitting, the extracted Evolution Associated Difference Spectra (EADS) clearly demonstrate that the GSB signal of the outer wall constantly decays during the probed time interval, while the inner wall signal rises on the short timescale as the result of the outer-inner walls energy transfer. This can be clearly visualized from Fig. S18, where we report the EADS obtained from global analysis performed on the data sets recorded at 80K, 140K and 260K. We further report in Figure S19 the kinetic traces taken at the maximum of the negative GSB/SE band with the correspondent fit obtained by global analysis. In the lower panel of each graph we also report the residuals of the fit. As it can be noticed, the residuals at both 80K and 140K display the oscillatory patterns observed at cryogenic temperature, which is not properly fitted through this global analysis procedure, only accounting for the exponential behavior of the signal. As noticed, the residuals of the fit at 260K is unstructured, since it only accounts for the noise of the measure.

Figure S18: *EADS* obtained by global analysis performed on the experimental broadband pump probe data at three different temperatures: 80K (left), 140K (center), 260K (right). The values on the legend indicates the time-constants associated to the spectral components.

Figure S19: *Kinetic traces* recorded on the maximum of the negative signal (GSB/ESA) of inner and outer wall, superimposed to the global fit obtained by global analysis (Glortaran software) by using a multi-exponential sequential scheme.

S3.4 TAS measurements at different excitation densities

Figure S20: *Single wavelength kinetics recorded on the minimum of the outer wall signal (GSB/SE at 504 THz) on LHNs in sugar matrix at 100K, at three different excitation densities. The three traces do not show appreciable differences, demonstrating that the excitation intensities used in this work are below the range of significant EEA.*

S3.5 Low Temperature pump-probe test on Rodhamine B

In order to definitely prove that the observed modulations of the transient signal are not ascribable to artefacts due to sample preparation, thickness or to the presence of the sugar matrix, we performed a TAS experiment on a test molecule, Rodhamine B, that was first dissolved in methanol and then embedded in the sugar matrix following the same preparation procedure used for the LHNs sample. Pump-probe spectra were collected for Rodhamine B films, placed in the same quartz cell used for C8S3 aggregates, at 100K, in order to reproduce the same experimental conditions used for LHNs. The results, reported in Figs. S21 and S22, show a no signs of the strong intensity modulations observed for the J-aggregate, while it is evident the presence of dumped oscillations, which can be assigned to impulsively excited vibrational modes, as often resolved in case of dyes excited with ultrashort pulses (see kinetic traces in Fig. S22) of frequency 210 cm^{-1} , in total agreement with literature data. [31, 32, 33]

(a)

(b)

Figure S21: *a) time-frequency map (a) and transient spectra (b) collected upon broadband excitation of Rodhamine B in sugar matrix at 100K.*

Figure S22: *Single wavelength kinetic recorded at the minimum of the bleaching signal (540 THz) of Rodhamine B in sugar matrix at 100K, showing damped oscillations with a frequency of 210 cm^{-1} .*

S4 Theoretical analysis of transient-absorption signals

S4.1 Single LHN

Let us introduce a subscript a which labels inner ($a = i$) and outer ($a = o$) LHNs. We will describe the spectroscopic response of a 's LHN by an effective model which comprises an electronic ground state $|g^{(a)}\rangle$, a pair of nonadiabatically coupled lowest excited electronic states $|e_1^{(a)}\rangle$ and $|e_2^{(a)}\rangle$ and a single Franck-Condon-active harmonic vibrational mode. The corresponding Hamiltonian $H^{(a)}$, which hereafter is referred to as the system Hamiltonian, is represented as a sum of the electronic ground-state Hamiltonian $H_g^{(a)}$ and the excited-state Hamiltonian $H_e^{(a)}$:

$$H^{(a)} = H_g^{(a)} + H_e^{(a)}. \quad (\text{S2})$$

Explicitly

$$H_g^{(a)} = |g^{(a)}\rangle h_0^{(a)} \langle g^{(a)}|,$$

$$H_e^{(a)} = \sum_{k,k'=1,2} |e_k^{(a)}\rangle h_{kk'}^{(a)} \langle e_{k'}^{(a)}|$$

where

$$h_{kk'}^{(a)} = (\epsilon_k^{(a)} + h_k^{(a)})\delta_{kk'} + \Delta^{(a)}(1 - \delta_{kk'}). \quad (\text{S3})$$

Here $\epsilon_k^{(a)}$ are the electronic excitation energies, $\Delta^{(a)}$ are the interstate nonadiabatic couplings, and vibrational Hamiltonians are defined as

$$h_k^{(a)} = \frac{\omega_{vib}^{(a)}}{2} \left\{ p_a^2 + (q_a - \bar{q}_k^{(a)})^2 \right\}$$

where q_a and p_a are the dimensionless coordinate and momentum, $\omega_{vib}^{(a)}$ is the vibrational frequency, and $\bar{q}_k^{(a)}$ is dimensionless displacement of the potential energy function in the excited electronic states $|e_1^{(a)}\rangle$ and $|e_2^{(a)}\rangle$ with respect to the electronic ground state $|g^{(a)}\rangle$ ($\bar{q}_0^{(a)} = 0$). We assume that the electronic state $|e_1^{(a)}\rangle$ is optically-bright while the electronic state $|e_2^{(a)}\rangle$ is optically-dark, so that the interaction of the system with laser pulses of the pump ($n = pu$) and the probe ($n = pr$) can be written in the dipole approximation, the Condon approximation, and the rotating-wave approximation as

$$H_F^{(a)}(t) = - \sum_{n=pu,pr} (X^\dagger \mathcal{E}_n(t) + X \mathcal{E}_n^*(t)). \quad (\text{S4})$$

Here

$$X_a \equiv \eta_a |g^{(a)}\rangle \langle e_1^{(a)}|, \quad X_a^\dagger \equiv \eta_a \langle e_1^{(a)}| \langle g^{(a)}| \quad (\text{S5})$$

are raising and lowering components of the transition dipole moment operator, η_a^2 is the oscillator strength, and

$$\mathcal{E}_n(t) = \lambda_n E_n(t - \tau_n) \exp\{i(\mathbf{k}_n \mathbf{r} - \omega_n t)\}, \quad (\text{S6})$$

where λ_n , \mathbf{k}_n , ω_n , $E_n(t)$, and τ_n denote the amplitude, wave vector, frequency, dimensionless envelope, and the central time of the pulses.

We are in the position now to introduce the master equation for the reduced density matrix of the system as ($\hbar = 1$)

$$\partial_t \rho^{(a)}(t) = \mathcal{L}^{(a)}(t) \rho^{(a)}(t) \quad (\text{S7})$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}^{(a)}(t) \rho^{(a)}(t) = -i[H^{(a)} + H_F^{(a)}(t), \rho^{(a)}(t)] + (\mathcal{R}^{(a)} + \mathcal{D}^{(a)}) \rho^{(a)}(t). \quad (\text{S8})$$

Here $\mathcal{R}^{(a)}$ is the vibrational relaxation/dephasing operator which accounts for the influence of all remaining vibrational modes of the LHN which are not included into the system Hamiltonian, while $\mathcal{D}^{(a)}$ is responsible for electronic dephasing. The master equation (S7) with the system Hamiltonian $H^{(a)}$ of Eq. (S2) is the working horse of the phenomenological description of the combined influence of electronically nonadiabatic

effects and vibrational relaxation/dephasing in various systems [3, 4, 5, 6], notably in electron transfer donor ($|e_1^{(a)}\rangle$) -- acceptor ($|e_2^{(a)}\rangle$) systems [7]. As for the application of the master equation (S7) to LHNs, we attribute $|e_1^{(a)}\rangle$ to the strongest optically-bright excitonic state (due to the symmetry, a single excitonic state frequently carries almost the entire oscillator strength in molecular aggregates [8]) while $|e_2^{(a)}\rangle$ represents an effective optically-dark charge-transfer state. However, this argumentation can only be used for heuristic justification of the model: due to enormous complexity of LHN systems, we cannot give a microscopic underpinning/parameterization of the Hamiltonian $H^{(a)}$. The validity of this description is verified a posteriori, since it gives a clear and insightful interpretation of the experimental results. See also Refs. [8, 9, 10] for the construction of microscopic (but much more complicated and multidimensional) models of optical responses of molecular aggregates.

The master equation (S7) should be solved with the initial condition

$$\rho^{(a)}(0) = |g^{(a)}\rangle\langle g^{(a)}| \rho_{eq}^{(a)} \quad (\text{S9})$$

where

$$\rho_{eq}^{(a)} = Z_a^{-1} \exp\{-\beta H^{(a)}\}. \quad (\text{S10})$$

Here $\beta = (k_B T)^{-1}$, Z_a is the partition function and T is the temperature. Eq. (S7) can be formally solved then as

$$\rho^{(a)}(t) = \mathcal{U}^{(a)}(t, 0) \rho^{(a)}(0) \quad (\text{S11})$$

where

$$\mathcal{U}^{(a)}(t, \tau) = \underset{\rightarrow}{\text{exp}}\left\{\int_{\tau}^t dt' \mathcal{L}^{(a)}(t')\right\} \quad (\text{S12})$$

is the time-evolution operator and the arrow denotes the time ordering.

S4.2 Coupled inner-outer LHN system

Up to now, we considered the inner and outer LHNs as non-interacting. It is well known, however, that energy transfer in double-walled LHN systems occurs on the timescale of several ps, that is on the timescale of the present experiment. To describe this energy transfer, we consider the two LHNs as a single system described by the Hamiltonian

$$H = H_{gg} + H_{ge+eg} + H_{ee}.$$

Here

$$H_{gg} = |g^{(i)}\rangle\langle g^{(o)}| (h_0^{(i)} + h_0^{(o)}) \langle e_1^{(i)}| \langle e_1^{(o)}|$$

refers to the situation where both LHNs are in the electronic ground state,

$$H_{ee} = \sum_{k,k',l,l'=1,2} |e_l^{(i)}\rangle\langle e_k^{(o)}| (h_{ll'}^{(i)} \delta_{kk'} + h_{kk'}^{(o)} \delta_{ll'}) \langle e_{k'}^{(o)}| \langle e_{l'}^{(i)}|$$

refers to the situation where both LHNs are electronically excited, and

$$H_{ge+eg} = H_{ge} + H_{eg} + U$$

refers to the situation where one of the LHNs is electronically excited, while the other is in its electronic ground state. Explicitly,

$$H_{ge} = \sum_{k,k'=1,2} |g^{(i)}\rangle\langle e_k^{(o)}| (h_0^{(i)} \delta_{kk'} + h_{kk'}^{(o)}) \langle e_{k'}^{(o)}| \langle g^{(i)}|$$

describes the electronically excited outer LHN,

$$H_{eg} = \sum_{k,k'=1,2} |g^{(o)}\rangle |e_k^{(i)}\rangle (h_0^{(o)} \delta_{kk'} + h_{kk'}^{(i)}) \langle e_{k'}^{(i)} | \langle g^{(o)} |$$

describes the electronically excited inner LHN, and

$$U = \sum_{k,k'=1,2} |g^{(o)}\rangle |e_k^{(i)}\rangle U_{kk'} \langle e_{k'}^{(o)} | \langle g^{(i)} | + H.c.$$

is the electronic coupling between the inner and outer LHNs, $U_{kk'}$ being the corresponding coupling matrix elements. The lowering component of the transition dipole moment operator assumes the form

$$X \equiv \eta^{(o)} |g^{(i)}\rangle |g^{(o)}\rangle \langle e_1^{(o)} | + \eta^{(i)} |g^{(o)}\rangle |g^{(i)}\rangle \langle e_1^{(i)} | + \sum_{k=1,2} \left\{ \eta^{(o)} |e_k^{(i)}\rangle |g^{(o)}\rangle \langle e_k^{(i)} | \langle e_1^{(o)} | + \eta^{(i)} |e_k^{(o)}\rangle |g^{(i)}\rangle \langle e_k^{(o)} | \langle e_1^{(i)} | \right\} \quad (\text{S13})$$

and the raising component, X^\dagger , is the Hermite conjugate of X .

The master equation for the reduced density matrix of the system of the coupled inner and outer LHNs reads

$$\partial_t \rho(t) = -i[H + H_F(t), \rho(t)] + (\mathcal{R} + \mathcal{D})\rho(t). \quad (\text{S14})$$

A model somewhat similar to the present one has been developed in Ref. [11]. The total Hamiltonian H comprises 9 electronic states and 2 vibrational modes. Transitions between the states described by the Hamiltonians H_{gg} and H_{ge+eg} , which are induced by first two terms in the transition dipole moment operator of Eq. (S13), are responsible for the ground-state bleach (GSB) and stimulated emission (SE) contributions to the transient-absorption signal. Transitions between the states described by the Hamiltonians H_{ge+eg} and H_{ee} , which are induced by the last two terms in the transition dipole moment operator of Eq. (S13), are responsible for the excited-state absorption (ESA) contribution to the transient-absorption signal. Assuming that vibrational dissipation/dephasing is described by multistate Redfield theory [7], the master equation equation (S14) can be straightforwardly integrated numerically and the transient-absorption pump-probe signal can be calculated by e.g. non-perturbative approach [12, 13] or by equation-of-motion phase-matching approach [14, 15]. However such a numerical solution depends on a number of free parameters and can get nothing profound to the understanding of the mechanisms of the energy transfer in double-walled LHNs. We thus prefer to simplify the model and express the transient-absorption signal of the coupled inner-outer LHN system in terms of the signals of individual inner and outer LHNs. This consideration, as demonstrated below, permits us to get extra insight into spectroscopic signatures of the outer-inner LHN energy transfer.

S4.3 Simplified description of the coupled inner-outer LHN pair

First, we restrict ourselves to the consideration of the GSB and SE contributions only, because the ESA contribution is caused by a simultaneous excitation of both LHNs. Second, we note that the experimental results of the present work do not show any signatures of electronically coherent energy transfer between the LHNs. On the contrary, we observe irreversible population transfer from the outer LHN to the inner LHN. This latter process can be described by the outer-to-inner transfer rate γ as specified by the operator \mathcal{G} . Thus the master equation (S14) transforms into

$$\partial_t \rho(t) = -i[\mathcal{H} + \mathcal{H}_F(t), \rho(t)] + (\mathcal{R} + \mathcal{D} + \mathcal{G})\rho(t). \quad (\text{S15})$$

Here

$$\rho(t) = \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{gg,gg}(t) & \rho_{gg,ge}(t) & \rho_{gg,eg}(t) \\ \rho_{ge,gg}(t) & \rho_{ge,ge}(t) & \rho_{ge,eg}(t) \\ \rho_{eg,gg}(t) & \rho_{eg,ge}(t) & \rho_{eg,eg}(t) \end{pmatrix}$$

is the 3×3 block density matrix,

$$\mathcal{H} = \begin{pmatrix} h_0^{(i)} + h_0^{(o)} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{1}h_0^{(i)} + \mathbf{h}^{(o)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{1}h_0^{(o)} + \mathbf{h}^{(i)} \end{pmatrix}$$

is the block-diagonal system Hamiltonian (2×2 matrix operators $\mathbf{h}^{(a)}$ are defined through their matrix elements $h_{kk'}^{(a)}$ per Eq. (S3)), the system-field interaction is described as

$$\mathcal{H}_F(t) = - \sum_{n=pu,pr} (\mathcal{X}^\dagger \mathcal{E}_n(t) + \mathcal{X} \mathcal{E}_n^*(t)). \quad (\text{S16})$$

where the transition dipole moment operators are defined as

$$\mathcal{X} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \boldsymbol{\eta}^{(o)} & \boldsymbol{\eta}^{(i)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{X}^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \boldsymbol{\eta}^{(o)} & 0 & 0 \\ \boldsymbol{\eta}^{(i)} & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$\boldsymbol{\eta}^{(a)} = (\eta_a, 0)$ are two-component vectors ($a = i, o$),

$$\mathcal{D}\rho(t) = -\xi \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \rho_{gg,ge}(t) & \rho_{gg,eg}(t) \\ \rho_{ge,gg}(t) & 0 & 0 \\ \rho_{eg,gg}(t) & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

describes optical dephasing with the rate ξ ,

$$\mathcal{G}\rho(t) = \gamma \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\rho_{ge,ge}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \rho_{eg,eg}(t) \end{pmatrix}$$

describes the irreversible population transfer from the outer to the inner LHN. Note that the relaxation operator can be decomposed into two components as

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_{gg} + \mathcal{R}_{ge+eg}, \quad [\mathcal{R}_{gg}, \mathcal{R}_{ge+eg}] = 0 \quad (\text{S17})$$

where \mathcal{R}_{gg} and \mathcal{R}_{ge+eg} act, correspondingly, within the gg and $ge + eg$ manifolds.

S4.4 Solution of Eq. (S15)

Master equation (S15) permits an approximate solution in terms of the master equation (S7) for individual non-interacting LHNs. Let us begin with the outer LHN. Tracing out vibrational degrees of freedom of the inner LHN in Eq. (S15), we obtain

$$\partial_t \rho^{(o)}(t) = (\mathcal{L}^{(o)}(t) - \gamma \mathcal{P}_e^{(o)}) \rho^{(o)}(t) \quad (\text{S18})$$

where $\mathcal{P}_e \rho^{(o)}(t)$ is the projector on the upper excited states $|e_1^{(o)}\rangle$ and $|e_2^{(o)}\rangle$ of the outer LHN. If the pump pulse is short compared to the system dynamics timescale, the results can be written as

$$\rho^{(o)}(t) = (e^{-\gamma t} \mathcal{P}_e^{(o)} + \mathcal{P}_g^{(o)}) \mathcal{U}^{(o)}(t, 0) \rho^{(o)}(0) \quad (\text{S19})$$

where $\mathcal{P}_g^{(o)}$ is the projector on the electronic ground state of the outer LHN, and the evolution operator $\mathcal{U}_e^{(a)}(t, 0)$ is defined per Eq. (S12). Eq. (S19) generates thus the following expression for the transient-absorption pump-probe signal of the outer LHN:

$$S^{(o)}(t, \omega) \approx S_{GSB}^{(o)}(t, \omega) + S_{SE}^{(o)}(t, \omega)e^{-\gamma t}. \quad (\text{S20})$$

Here the subscripts GSB and SE label the corresponding contributions to the transient absorption signal obtained without inter-outer LHN coupling ($\gamma = 0$).

Let us now concentrate on the inner LHN. Tracing out vibrational degrees of freedom of the outer LHN in Eq. (S15), we obtain

$$\partial_t \rho^{(i)}(t) = \mathcal{L}^{(i)}(t) \rho^{(i)}(t) + \gamma \mathcal{P}_e^{(i)} \rho_0^{(i)}(0) \sigma_e^{(o)}(t) \quad (\text{S21})$$

where $\bar{\rho}_e^{(o)}(t) = \text{Tr}\{\mathcal{P}_e \rho^{(o)}(t)\}$ is the total pump-pulse induced population of the upper excited state of the outer LHN. Assuming instantaneous excitation, we obtain

$$\bar{\rho}_e^{(o)}(t) \approx e^{-\gamma t} \text{Tr}\{\mathcal{P}_e \mathcal{U}^{(o)}(0, 0) \rho^{(o)}(0)\} = \bar{\rho}_e^{(o)}(0) e^{-\gamma t}$$

where $\bar{\rho}_e^{(o)} \sim \eta_o^2$. Then

$$\rho^{(i)}(t) = \mathcal{U}_e^{(i)}(t, 0) \rho^{(i)}(0) + \gamma \bar{\rho}_e^{(o)} \int_0^t dt' e^{-\gamma t'} \mathcal{U}^{(i)}(t, t') \mathcal{P}_e^{(i)} \rho^{(i)}(0).$$

If $e^{-\gamma t'}$ decays relatively fast we obtain then

$$\rho^{(i)}(t) \approx \mathcal{U}_e^{(i)}(t, 0) \left\{ 1 + (1 - e^{-\gamma t}) \bar{\rho}_e^{(o)}(0) \mathcal{P}_e^{(i)} \right\} \rho^{(i)}(0).$$

Finally, taking into account that

$$\bar{\rho}_e^{(i)}(0) = \text{Tr}\{\mathcal{P}_e \mathcal{U}^{(i)}(0, 0) \rho^{(i)}(0)\}$$

where $\bar{\rho}_e^{(i)} \sim \eta_i^2$ we obtain

$$S^{(i)}(t, \omega) \approx S_{GSB}^{(i)}(t, \omega) + S_{SE}^{(i)}(t, \omega) (1 + \sigma (1 - e^{-\gamma t})) \quad (\text{S22})$$

where $\sigma = \bar{\rho}_e^{(o)}(0) / \bar{\rho}_e^{(i)}(0) \sim \eta_o^2 / \eta_i^2$ is the ratio of the initial populations of the outer and inner LHNs induced by the pump pulse. Here the subscripts GSB and SE label the corresponding contributions to the transient absorption signal obtained without inter-outer LHN coupling ($\gamma = 0$).

Eqs. (S20) and (S22) are the main theoretical results of the present section. They demonstrate how transient absorption signals of individual LHNs ($\gamma = 0$) are related to the corresponding signals of the coupled LHNs ($\gamma \neq 0$).

S4.5 Numerical evaluation of the signals

For the illustrative simulations shown below, we have selected the following model parameters. The vibrational frequency is fixed at $\omega_{vib}^{(a)} = 0.0153$ eV (123.5 cm^{-1}), so that the fundamental vibrational period is $2\pi / \omega_{vib}^{(a)} = 270$ fs matches the period of the vibrational oscillations in the transient absorption signals (see below). Dimensionless displacements of the excited-state potential energy surfaces are set at to $\bar{q}_1^{(a)} = -2$ (bright state) and $\bar{q}_2^{(a)} = -1$ (dark state). The interstate electronic coupling is $\Delta^{(a)} = 0.0023$ eV (18.5 cm^{-1}). The difference between the electronic energies of the bright and dark states is $\epsilon_1^{(a)} - \epsilon_2^{(a)} = \omega_{vib}^{(a)}$. The vibrational relaxation operator \mathcal{R} in the master equation (S7) is treated within the multi-level Redfield formalism [7, 16]. The bath spectral function is taken in the Ohmic form $J(\omega) = \eta \omega \exp\{-\omega / \omega_c\}$ with the cutoff frequency $\omega_c = \omega_{vib}^{(a)}$. The dimensionless parameter $\eta = 0.1$ corresponds to a rather weak vibrational dissipation. Electronic dephasing rate is $\xi = 0.075$ eV (605 cm^{-1}). The pulse envelopes are assumed to be

Gaussian,

$$E_a(t) = \exp \left\{ -4 \ln 2 (t/\mathcal{T}_a)^2 \right\}, \quad (\text{S23})$$

$\mathcal{T}_a = 60$ fs being the pulse duration (full width at half maximum). The carrier frequencies of the pulses were taken in resonance with the bright electronic state of the outer LHN.

Transient absorption signals are evaluated via the two-pulse equation-of-motion phase-matching approach [14, 15]. The master equation (S7) is converted into matrix form by an expansion in terms of the eigenstates of the system Hamiltonian $H^{(a)}$. The field-matter interaction is treated numerically exactly. The fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme is used for propagations of the reduced density matrices (see Ref. [3, 15] for computational details).

Note parenthetically that experiments of Ref. [17] showed that a relatively low-frequency 315 cm^{-1} vibrational mode is responsible for the exciton energy transfer in double-walled light-harvesting LHNs at room temperature. A hump around 1.5 ps is a signature of the electronic revival, which is caused by the electron-vibrational coupling $\Delta^{(a)}$ and is similar to the celebrated electronic Rabi-beating in two-level systems. In the present case, however, the revival is of vibronic origin. Hence the position of the hump is renormalized by the vibrational mode and cannot be directly traced back to the model parameters. Nevertheless, $2\pi/\Delta^{(a)} = 1.6$ ps matches, accidentally, the position of the hump quite well. Furthermore, the outer-to-inner LHN energy transfer time $\gamma^{-1} = 439$ fs allows to simultaneously describe the inner and outer LHN kinetics.

S4.6 Computational study of the Franck-Condon activity of the C8S3 monomer

In order to understand the origin of the vibrational motion that is responsible for the observed quantum beatings in the PP signal we have performed a computational study of the Franck-Condon activity of the vibrational modes of the C8S3 monomer unit. The molecular geometries of the ground state and of the first excited state of a model C8S3 unit have been optimized using density functional theory (DFT) and its time-dependent counterpart (TFD-DFT); in both cases the standard Becke, three parameter, Lee-Yang Parr exchange-functional (B3LYP) has been used in combination with a 6-31G(d,p) basis set. Vibrational normal modes of the ground state have computed using standard Hessian analysis, and the Duschinsky transformation has been computed with the assumption that the normal modes in the first excited singlet and those of the ground state are subject to a displacement of the equilibrium position but do not change their direction (*i.e.* the Duschinsky rotation matrix is assumed to be the identity matrix). This approximation is known to provide quite satisfactory results for cyanine-like dyes.[35] The resulting vibronic activity is shown in figure S23, and the computed absorption spectrum of the monomer is given in figure S24.

Figure S23: *Huang-Rhys factors for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ electronic transition computed at TFD-DFT/B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level of theory. The inset clearly shows the two vibrations at 117 cm^{-1} and 131 cm^{-1} with a relatively strong Franck-Condon activity.*

Figure S24: Absorption profile for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ electronic transition computed at TFD-DFT/B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level of theory using Toyozawa and Kubo generating function approach. The experimental spectrum has been shifted and scaled to match the position of the maximum of the computed spectrum.

We notice the presence of two vibrations at 117 and 131 cm^{-1} with a relatively strong HR factor (see inset of figure S23). The absorption spectrum is only in qualitative agreement with the experimental data probably due to the level of calculation, however both the position of the observed shoulder and its overall bandwidth are correctly reproduced. This result support the qualitatively correct picture provided by our computations.

Finally we report a sketch of the two vibrations at 117 cm^{-1} and 131 cm^{-1} in Fig. S25.

Figure S25: Sketch of the two vibrational modes of the C8S3 monomer which are believed to be responsible for the quantum beats observed in the PP experiment. The sulfate groups and the long alkyl chains have been replaced by simpler methyl groups.

S4.7 Theory-inspired fitting

The above described model can be employed for the construction of the fitting procedure which can be conveniently used for the quantitative analysis of the experimental signals:

$$S^{(a)}(t, \omega) = -(A_1(t) + A_2(t) + A_3(t) + \chi^{(a)} A_4(t)). \quad (\text{S24})$$

Here t is time in picoseconds, $\chi^{(o)} = 1$, $\chi^{(i)} = -1$,

$$A_1(t) = a_1 \cos((a_2 + a_3 t^2)t - a_4) \vartheta(t - t_0),$$

$$A_2(t) = a_5 \exp(-a_6 t) + a_7,$$

$$A_3(t) = a_8 \exp(-a_9(t - a_{10})^2),$$

$$A_4(t) = (1 - \vartheta(t - t_0))a_{11} \exp(-a_{12}(t - t_0)),$$

a_k and t_0 are real-valued fitting parameters, and $\vartheta(t)$ is the theta function ($\vartheta(t) = 1$ for $t < 0$, $\vartheta(t) = 0$ for $t > 0$) which in the present work is chosen in the continuous form

$$\vartheta(t) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\arctan(50t)}{\pi}.$$

Specifically, $A_1(t)$ describes first few high-amplitude vibrational beatings (a_3 is responsible for the decrease of the beating amplitudes as well as for a non-cosine shape of the beatings), $A_2(t)$ gives a constant background and possible decrease of its amplitude, $A_3(t)$ reproduces the electronic revival centered at $t = a_{10}$, and $A_4(t)$ is responsible for outer-to-inner LHN energy transfer (cf. Eqs. (S20) and (S22)) so that a_{12} can be identified with γ .

S5 2D electronic spectroscopy maps

Figure S26: 2DES maps collected at different population times TPOP at 100K used for cross peak analysis.

Figure S27: *2DES maps collected at different population times TPOP at 260K used for cross peaks analysis.*

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